

Influence of Boko Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics at Internally Displaced Persons Camps in North-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The research was carried out to ascertain the influence of Boko-haram insurgency on students' enrollment in economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States. The research adopted a Correlational survey research design. There were two objectives and two research questions and two hypotheses that guided the study; population of the study is 2,349 male and female students. while the sample consists one hundred and three (103) students, using purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts, 2 from economics education department while 1 from measurement and evaluation all from Ebonyi State University Abakaliki. The research questions were answered using bivariate correlation (specifically, the Pearson's r) and linear regression. The hypotheses were tested at 95% confidence level using the linear regression analysis. The study reveals a negative relationship (-.9004) between insurgency influence and enrolment in schools in the IDP camp. The result further revealed that the coefficient of determination (r^2) is .81071. While enrolment for male and females are negative. relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively. It was concluded that students' enrolment, in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in North-East, Nigeria is negatively influenced by Boko-Haram insurgency. The study recommended based of the findings that Government should evolve more robust approach to managing security issues in Borno and Yobe States, adequate security should be provided to IDP camps especially in schools within the camps to give the students assurance of their safety.

Keywords: influence, insurgency, enrollment, IDPs

Introduction

The building block of life is education. Education is a veritable instrument and a cornerstone for the building and sustenance of any nation (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019). Whatever a nation becomes depends on the type and quality of education provided for her citizenry, because no nation can rise above her education system, since the school is the mirror of the society and agent

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of social change through education (Ikwumelu, 2019). Education is a module and mirror-image of social realities. Social realities are maintained, and reproduced by education and are at the same time changed by effective education (Ikwumelu, 2019). Education is very effective instrument of change, and a vehicle through which skills, knowledge and attitudes are acquired, transferred, or modified (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2013). To acquire transform and modify society of any nation the need to develop the country's economy is inevitable. Education is widely accepted as a major instrument for promoting socio-economic, political and cultural development.

Economics is a Social Science which deals with the means by which limited resources are used to satisfy competitive wants. Economics is concerned with the patterns of production, distribution, exchange and consumption of goods and services. Economics as a subject, offers knowledge in the relationship between a given economic system and the way of life of the people concerned. According to Ameachi (2016) Economics is defined as a social science subject that studies human behaviors in the effort to allocate scarce resources efficiently and effectively in order to minimize cost. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, (NERDC, 2008), opined that there is a need to make the post-basic Economics curriculum responsive and relevant to Nigeria's quest to be among the top 20 players of the world economy come 2030.

Despite the important roles of Economics subject there is serious complaint that it lacks in developing analytical mind, critical thinking, in making judicious allocation of resources in the process of equipping Secondary School students with skills that enhanced their meaningful contributions to the economy,(WAEC Chief Examiner, 2019).The Chief Examiner while commenting on 2019 result, disclosed that there was a decline in students' achievement in Economics subject when compared with the previous years. Also, the available statistics at Education Resource Centres (ERC) in Maiduguri and Damaturu, the states capital revealed that no student scored distinction in Economics in 2022 West African Examination Council (WAEC) Examination in the two states (Education Resource Centre, 2023).

This trend of student's poor achievement could be attributed to frequent insurgence in the areas. As a result of this the education system in Borno and Yobe states has been devastated by nearly twelve years of armed conflict between Nigerian government and the Boko Haram insurgencies, (UNICEF,2020). Boko Haram insurgency has targeted government facilities, especially public schools for attack with 279 schools forced to close in Borno and Yobe States (NUT, 2019), since the Boko Haram incursion from June 16,2009- to date. This violence led the Borno state government to close all public schools in 22 out of 27 Local Government Areas for at least seven years (NUT, 2019) and also the violence led Yobe State Government to close 126 public schools in twelve Local Government Areas out of 17 in the state (Human Right Watch and NUT, 2019). The blanket closure has since affected Borno and Yobe States, as they are among the states that generally fall under the rubric of Educationally Less Advantaged States (ELAS) common classification used by educational planners in Nigeria (Abubakar, Mohammed and Yagana, 2018). School children were killed, schools burnt, facilities destroyed, abductions and kidnapping of school girls (Chibok Girls School in Borno state and Dafchi Girls School in Yobe state), persistent, threat, fears and displacement led to a high level of trauma in citizens (UNISCEF, 2019).

Many of the School facilities were destroyed and high population in the affected states have been displaced leading to thousands of children being out of school (UNICEF, 2019). The death toll of students was 228 while 178 teachers were killed (UNICEF, 2019) Therefore, it is not only the students and teachers that are lost but also all the classrooms, teaching materials, libraries, laboratories, school clinics and school records leaving students with nowhere to learn and teachers nowhere to teach. As a result of these attacks in Borno and Yobe states Government adopted double- shift schooling strategies to ensure the basic education need for IDPs students in schools nearby.

Double- shift schooling programme allowed normal students to attend classes from early-morning until-mid day (7:30 am to: 12 pm) for children from the school community but with a slight adjustment of school hours to allow for Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) students to run programme from the late afternoon to evening (1: pm to 6: pm) with their teachers, and each group has principal to govern the school activities (MNE and NUT, 2019). The schooling strategy was adopted to ensure continuation of basic Education needs for the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) students in nearby schools which have limited resources/infrastructure within the states capitals.

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Studies in Nigeria have established negative effects of insurgency on education and its stakeholders. Addullahi, Amadu and Habu (2017) observed that the level of school attendance under the crisis situation has been low. Musa and Nwachukwu (2014) compared self-identity of 600 adolescents displaced as a result of Boko-Haram insurgency with the non-displaced who are far from insurgency affected areas. Displaced adolescents were found to exhibit identity confusion –related symptoms which may exert adverse effect on learning. Adebayo (2014) found that as an insurgency group, Boko-Haram fighters force their ideology on people through bombings, abduction and slaughtering of human beings, creating palpable fear and sense of insecurity in the polity. Hamman-Tukur, Atsua, Nwachukwu (2016) investigated the impact of boko-haram insurgency as perceived by teachers, administrators and students in Secondary Schools in Maiduguri and found that normal schools have been shut down, staff and student killed, abduction of teachers and students, took places, as well as destruction on of school facilities and increased absenteeism.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study was to ascertain the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in Double-shift Schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States
2. The influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female Students' enrollment Economics in Double-shift Schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Research Questions

This study was designed to answer the following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?
2. What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for the study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. HO₁: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States
2. HO₂: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Research Methodology

The study adopted a correlational survey research design. This design seeks to establish relationships between variables or direct influence of one variable (X) on another variable(s) (Y). This study adopted correlational survey because its focus is on establishing the direct influence/impact of Boko Haram insurgency on school enrolment in Economics at the internally displaced Persons (IDP) camps.

The study was carried out in Borno state. The choice for these areas was because it is devastated by Boko- Haram Insurgency leading to destruction of school records, facilities and buildings, as well as killing, and adoption of students and teachers in the areas. The areas housed largest number of the internally displaced persons in the country which influenced students' enrollment in Economics subject. The population for this study was 2,349 (Male:1500 and Female:849) senior secondary school class two (SSII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in IDP camps in Borno state. The sample size for this study was One Hundred and Three (103) comprises (Male:63 and Female:40) IDPs SS11 Economics students during the 2023/2024 academic session.

The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. both secondary and primary data collection for this current study were used. these include: Students school statutory records on Enrolment (SSSROE) to elicit record of student's

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enrolment in economics. Research questions were answered using bivariate correlation (specifically the Pearson's r). Hypotheses were tested at 95% confidence level using the linear regression analysis.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?

Table 1: Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Computed r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std Error
-.9004	.81071	.80884	6.6397

Source: Statutory Records of Students'

Summary of result on Table 1 reveals a negative relationship (-.9004) correlation between Boko-Haram insurgency influence and enrollment in Economics Education Among Secondary School Students Internally Displaced Persons Camps. The Table further revealed that the coefficient of determination (r²) is .81071. This implies that 81% of school enrolment in the IDP camp is determined by the level of insurgency.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States?

Table 2: Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States

Gender Categories	Computed r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std Error
Male	-.8887	.78974	.78641	7.13833
Female	-.9243	.85432	.85028	5.77953

Source: Statutory Records of Students'

As shown on Table 2 the Influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is negative. As seen on Table 2 the relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively for males and for females. The coefficient determination of males is .7897 implying that males has approximately 79% while for females is 85%.

Hypotheses 1

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States.

Summary of result is presented on Table 3

Table 3: Significance of the influence Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Computed	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig of T
-.9004	.81071	.80884	6.6397	-.900394	20.798	.000

Source: Statutory Records of Students'

As shown on Table 3, the significant of T is .000 while the alpha level is 0.05. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the alpha level is greater than the Sig. of T. Based on this decision rule the research rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in Economic in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States.

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Hypotheses 2

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on male and female students' in Economics in double-shift schooling at internally displaced persons' camps in Borno and Yobe States

Summary of result is presented on Table 4

Table 4: Significance of influence of the Boko-Haram insurgency influence and enrollment on male and female in Economics Education Among Secondary School Students Internally Displaced Persons Camps in Borno and Yobe States.

Gender	Computed r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig of T
Male	-.8887	.78974	.78641	7.13833	-.888675	15.383	.0000
Female	-.9243	.85432	.85028	5.77953	-.924295	14.530	.0000

Result of data analysis summarized on Table 10 indicates that for males the alpha level (0.05) is greater than the Sig of T (.0000). Based on the decision rule the researcher concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on Male Students enrollment in double-shift Schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant. The summary of result also indicates that for the females the alpha level is greater than the T sig value. As such the researcher also concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on female Students enrollment at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

The researcher discussed the findings of this study based on the two research questions and two null hypotheses that guided this study. The discussions were presented in two themes as follows:

Summary of result on Table 1 reveals a negative relationship (-.9004) between insurgency level and enrolment in schools in the IDP camp. The Table further revealed that the coefficient of determination (r²) is .81071. This implies that 81% of school enrolment in economics in the IDP camp is determined by the level of insurgency. On the test of significance of the relationship shown on Table 2 the significant of T is .000 while the alpha level is 0.05. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the alpha level is greater than the Sig. of T. Based on this decision rule the research rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that the influence of Boko-Haram insurgency on students' enrollment in double-shift schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant.

As shown on Table 3 the relationships between insurgency and enrolment for male and also for females are negative. As seen on Table 4, the relationships are -.8887 and -.9243 respectively for males and for females. The coefficient of determination of insurgency on enrolment for males is .7897 implying that for males approximately 79% of enrolment of males is attributable to insurgency while for female it is approximately 85%. The researcher, in the tests of hypothesis, tested the significance of the relationships across gender with respect to levels of insurgency and enrolment. Result of data analysis summarized indicates that for males the alpha level (0.05) is greater than the Sig of T (.0000). Based on the decision rule the researcher concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on Male Students enrollment in double-shift Schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant. The summary of result also indicates that for the females the alpha level is greater than the T sig value. As such the researcher also concludes that the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on female Students enrollment in double-shift Schooling at the IDPs camps in Borno and Yobe States is statistically significant.

The finding agreed with the finding of Addullahi, Amadu and Habu (2017) who observed that the level of school enrollment and attendance under the crisis situation has been low. Musa and Nwachukwu (2014) compared self-identity of 600 adolescents displaced as a result of Boko-Haram insurgency with the non-displaced who are far from insurgency affected areas. Displaced adolescents were found to exhibit identity confusion-related symptoms which exert adverse effect on their willingness to get enrolled in schools. Adebayo (2014) found that as an insurgency group, Boko-Haram fighters force their ideology (that

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education is evil) on people through bombings, abduction and slaughtering of human beings, creating palpable fear and sense of insecurity in the polity. This ideology sometimes becomes permanent and obviously manifest in their willingness to enroll in schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study: it is therefore concluding that students' enrolment at internally displaced persons' camps in north-east, Nigeria is negatively influenced by Boko Haram Insurgency. The study revealed a significant influence of Boko Haram insurgency for both male and female students' attendance to schools in the IDP camps. Also, Students' attendance to school in double-shift schooling at internally displaced person's camps in north-east, Nigeria is negatively influenced by Boko Haram Insurgency. The study also revealed a negative influence of Boko Haram insurgency for both male and female students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should evolve a more robust approach to managing security issues in Borno and Yobe States.
2. Adequate security should be provided to IDP camps especially in schools within the camps to give the students assurance of their safety. This will obviously increase their willingness to enroll, attend classes and also achieve in their respective subjects' while effective counselling services should be provided to people in the IDP camps. The focus will be on re-orientation of the members of IDP camps on the importance of education and the need to enroll and attend classes.

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